

Assessing the Continuum of Maternal and Child Health: Correlations Between ANC Indicators and Immunization Coverage in Rwanda

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Background

Maternal and Child health is a key part of public health and a major factor in a country's overall health. Antenatal care (ANC) and childhood immunization are two of the most cost-effective, and proved to be evidence-based interventions for reducing maternal and child morbidity and mortality [1][2]. ANC provides a well-structured opportunity to monitor pregnancy, detect and also manage complications that may arise from pregnancy, deliver preventive treatments, and prepare mothers for safe delivery [3]. Immunization, on the other hand, protects infants and young children against life threatening infectious diseases which this reduces the under-five mortality rates [4].

Globally, according to the World Health Organization (WHO) recommended a minimum of eight ANC contacts during pregnancy, with the first contact occurring in the first trimester [5][6]. These contacts were thought and designed to optimize the outcomes that comes from pregnancy by ensuring timely screening, education on health related, nutritional supplementation, and early intervention for risk conditions [7]. Similarly to this, WHO and UNICEF immunization schedules recommends that children should receive DTP-HepB-Hib3 (DTP3) in infancy (around 14 weeks) and receive also Measles & Rubella (MR2) in early toddlerhood (15-18 months), among other vaccines [8]. Together, these interventions helps in forming an integrated continuum of care from pregnancy though early childhood.

ANC visits presents a unique platform to help in promoting and preparing for mother to bring their children for immunization [9]. Through repeated contact with the health system during pregnancy, mothers are educated and well informed on the immunization schedule, encouraged to deliver in health facilities, and motivated to return for postnatal and child vaccination appointments [10] [11]. Different studies have shown that women who attend more ANC visits are more likely to have their children fully immunized, from here you understand that there is a link between attending ANC visits and bringing your children to be vaccinated [12] [13] [14] [15].

However, the great strength of this relationship can vary due to several factors; one is service integration where whether the ANC and immunization services are coordinated within the same facility or coordinated in outreach programs, the other thing is the health system performance; making an assumptions that there are availability of vaccines, trained staff, and reliable supply chains. Moreover, we can't explicitly forget the sociocultural and economic barriers that can affect this relationship because mother's knowledge, beliefs and access to transportation can be a key factor to this as well. Lastly, it is the data completeness and reporting; accurate measurement depends on consistent health facility reporting for both the ANC and immunization.

Rwanda has made significant progress in improving maternal and child health indicators over the last two decades [16] [17]. Major investment has been made in primary healthcare, community-based health insurance, and not forgetting the contribution of health facilities especially health centers that have contributed to high ANC attendance and increasing immunization coverage [18]. National guidelines emphasizes more on early ANC initiation, and completing the recommended ANC contacts, but also adhering to the Expanded Programme on Immunization (EPI) schedule [19].

Despite these progress, some challenges are still remaining. Data completeness and quality vary across facilities and years. Rural and hard to reach populations sometimes face service gaps and high coverage at the national level can show some disparities between facilities [20]. Additionally, the relationship between the ANC utilizations and immunization uptake has not been fully measured at the facility level but also at the national level as there few studies that have done it using the routine health information system (RHIS) data to try to create an understanding where integration efforts are most effective and where they need strengthening, there's still a gap in understanding this [21] [22].

Although not always constant, there is evidently strong correlation between ANC performance and vaccination coverage. Using facility level data spanning several years extracted from the Rwanda Health management information system (HMIS), we examined relationships between several ANC indicators and immunization coverage (DTP3 and MR2) to;

- Identify which ANC indicators are most strongly correlated with immunization outcomes
- Look high performing facilities where strong ANC and immunization results coincide
- Detect facilities with mismatched performance which may signal service delivery gaps
- Examine trends overtime including the effect of expanded facility reported in recent years

This analysis gave us an opportunity to assess how changes in reporting completeness and coverage including the large increase in the number of facilities that are submitting HMIS data from xxx onwards affect interpretations of coverage data.

Study Objectives

Primary objectives

To assess the relationship between selected ANC indicators and immunization coverage (DTP3 and MR2) at the health facility level using HMIS data

Secondary Objectives:

1. To identify high and low performing facilities for ANC and examine corresponding immunization performance
2. To evaluate trends and lagged relationships between ANC and immunization over time
3. To examine the effects of reporting completeness and facility expansion on per facility performance metrics

Methods

Study Design and Setting

We conducted a retrospective facility level analysis using routinely collected service delivery data from Rwanda's Health management Information System (HMIS). The analysis focused on the relationship between antenatal care (ANC) indicators and childhood immunization coverage for two vaccines DTP-HepB-Hib3 (DTP3) and Measles & Rubella second dose (MR2) over multiple reporting years. Rwanda's HMIS aggregates data from public and private facilities nationwide covering both the urban and rural settings.

Data Sources

We extracted data from HMIS indicator files for ANC and immunization. Eight ANC indicators were used;

1. ANC 4 standard contacts
2. ANC 8 standard contacts
3. ANC first contact (first trimester)
4. ANC new registrations (all ages)
5. ANC new registrations aged 14-17 years
6. ANC new registrations aged 18-19 years
7. ANC new registrations under 14 years
8. ANC risk pregnancies (including pregnancies under age 15)

We used also two immunization indicators;

- DTP-HepB-Hib3 (DTP3)
- Measles & Rubella second dose (MR2)

Each dataset contained a “period” variable meaning a reporting year, Organization unit (facility name), and value (service count), plus unused or empty columns (Numerator, Denominator, factor, multiplier, divisor)

Data Cleaning and Merging

We kept only “Period”, “Organization unit”, and “Value” from each file and renamed “Value” to the relevant indicator name. All ANC and immunization files were merged on “Period” and “Organization unit” using an outlier join to create a master dataset with one row per facility year.

Missing Data Assessment and Variable Selection

To assess the missing values, we computed the number and percentage of missing values for each indicator. Four ANC indicators had low missingness (<6%):

- ANC 4 standard contacts
- ANC first contact (first trimester)
- ANC new registrations (all ages)
- ANC risk pregnancies

These were kept and retained for main correlation analysis alongside DTP3 and MR2. Variables with high missingness (e.g., ANC 8 contacts, ANC age-disaggregated registrations) were excluded from primary correlation analysis but examined descriptively

Statistical Analysis

Correlation Analysis

For each ANC-immunization pair that we kept that has low missingness, we calculated Pearson’s correlation coefficient (r), p -values, and 95% confidence intervals using Fisher’s z -transformation. Significance thresholds were denoted or written as $p < 0.05$ (*), $p < 0.01$ (**), and $p < 0.001$ (***). Analysis were based on pairwise complete cases.

Facility performance comparison

We ranked facilities by average ANC new registrations to identify the top and bottom 10 performers and examined their average DTP3 and MR2 counts. Facilities with zero or missing immunization data were excluded from this comparison to avoid skew from non-reporting sites

Time-series and lag analysis

We aggregated counts by year to produce annual averages and tested correlations between ANC and immunization for the same year and for ANC lagged by one and two years. Lags were done for us to reflect the timing of vaccine administration (DTP ~ 3-4 months after birth and MR2 ~ 15-18 months)

Furthermore, we also examined annual trends using per-facility averages (sum of indicator values divided by the number of reporting facilities for that year) to adjust for changes in reporting coverage

Reporting completeness

We counted the number of facilities we have in the dataset reporting non-missing data for each indicator by year and calculated the percentage relative to both (a) the global number of facilities appearing in the dataset and (b) the number of facilities reporting any indicator that year. This showed an increase in facilities reporting in 2023-2024 which was considered in interpreting per facilities averages

Software

All data management, analysis, and visualization were conducted in Python 3.11 using pandas (data processing), a statistical test we used “scipy.stats”, while on visualization we used “matplotlib/ seaborn”

Results

Descriptive Statistics

The merged HMIS dataset covered 2017-2024, having 1271 health facilities. Facilities reporting remained stable looking at table 1 below, it shows that from 2017 to 2022, it was stable with (~540-610) facilities contributed in the ANC data and 550-570 reporting immunization data each year. In 2023, the number of reporting facilities more than doubled to 1,366 for ANC and 1,314 for immunization. By 2024, reporting expanded more further to over 1,550 facilities.

Table 1. Number of facilities reporting ANC and immunization indicators by year, Rwanda HMIS 2017-2024

Year	Facilities_reporting_ANC	Facilities_reporting_DTP3	Facilities_reporting_MR2
2017	534	558	558
2018	544	561	561
2019	608	576	576
2020	592	554	553
2021	598	555	555
2022	611	567	567
2023	1366	1314	1314
2024	1566	1555	1555

Table 2 below summarises the description statistics for ANC and immunization indicators across all facilities and years.

Among the ANC variables, ANC new registrations recorded the highest average counts (mean =438, SD =585, maximum =13,342) show the high variability across the facilities. ANC first contact (first trimester) and ANC 4 contacts also showed significant averages, but with ANC 8 contacts and age disaggregated registration variables (14-17 years, 18-19 years, under 14) were low showing lower population subgroups and increased missingness in reporting.

Furthermore, for immunization variables, DTP3 and MR2 showed comparable averages for immunization results (406 and 380 respectively) with a large variation between facilities (maximums of 3,972 and 3,285). In line with variations with facility sizes, catchment population and reporting completeness, this points on to heterogeneity or variability in service volumes.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of ANC and immunization variables (2017-2024)

Variable	count	mean	std	min	25%	50%	75%	max
ANC_4_contacts	6416.0	170.98	212.17	0.0	0.0	116.0	265.00	4327.0
ANC_8_contacts	524.0	24.63	41.47	0.0	0.0	5.0	32.25	266.0
ANC_first_contact_1st_trimester	6416.0	199.04	222.10	0.0	0.0	154.0	312.00	3773.0
ANC_new_registrations	6419.0	437.60	585.21	0.0	0.0	360.0	651.50	13342.0
ANC_new_reg_14_17	3535.0	3.77	6.88	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.00	58.0
ANC_new_reg_18_19	4179.0	18.79	27.72	0.0	0.0	4.0	30.00	271.0
ANC_new_reg_under_14	3535.0	0.10	1.19	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.00	43.0
ANC_risk_pregnancies	6416.0	56.74	93.21	0.0	0.0	20.0	80.00	1254.0
DTP3	6240.0	406.10	442.14	0.0	0.0	340.0	619.00	3972.0
MR2	6239.0	379.87	396.13	0.0	0.0	323.0	593.50	3285.0

Correlation Between ANC and Immunization

Initially, we first assessed correlations between all ANC indicators and immunization outcomes (DTP3 and MR2) we have. However, after reviewing the results, we recognized that missing data could bias estimates. Several ANC indicators mostly ANC 8 contacts and age-specific new registrations, had very high levels of missingness exceeding 30%. To reduce potential bias, we excluded these high missingness variables from the main correlation analysis. The retained set of indicators with acceptable less than 30% missingness include; ANC 4contacts, ANC first contact in the first trimester, ANC new registrations, ANC risk pregnancies. Using this reduced set, all ANC variables were positively and significantly correlated with both DTP3 and MR2 ($p < 0.001$ for all). The strongest correlation were observed for ANC new registrations ($r = 0.804$) with DTP3; $r = 0.793$ with MR2) and ANC first contact (first trimester) ($r = 0.757$ with DTP3; $r = 0.775$ with MR2). ANC risk pregnancies showed the weakest association but still significance association

($r \approx 0.62$). Confidence intervals confirmed that these correlations were robust with all 95% CIs excluding zero.

Table 3. Correlation between ANC indicators (low-missingness subset) and immunization outcomes, Rwanda HMIS 2017- 2024)

ANC Variable	Immunization Variable	N	r (stars)	P-value	95% CI Lower	95% CI Upper
ANC_4_contacts	DTP3	6029	0.698***	0.0	0.684	0.710
ANC_4_contacts	MR2	6029	0.711***	0.0	0.699	0.724
ANC_first_contact_1st_trimester	DTP3	6029	0.757***	0.0	0.746	0.768
ANC_first_contact_1st_trimester	MR2	6029	0.775***	0.0	0.765	0.785
ANC_new_registrations	DTP3	6029	0.804***	0.0	0.795	0.813
ANC_new_registrations	MR2	6029	0.793***	0.0	0.784	0.802
ANC_risk_pregnancies	DTP3	6029	0.617***	0.0	0.601	0.633
ANC_risk_pregnancies	MR2	6029	0.621***	0.0	0.606	0.637

* Indicate significance level: *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$

The correlation heatmap is provided in **Supplementary Figure 1**. Figure 1 (pairwise scatterplots with regression lines) shows an additional illustration of the correlation pattern that there's a significant positive correlation between ANC indicators and immunization outcomes.

Figure 1. Pairwise scatterplots (with regression lines) of ANC indicators versus DTP3 and MR2, Rwanda HMIS 2017-2024

Pairplot: ANC vs Immunization Variables

Facility Level Performance

We evaluated the associated DTP3 and MR2 outputs of the top 10 facilities ranked by average ANC new registrations in order to find out whether facility-level ANC volumes coincide with immunization outcomes.

Overall, on most cases we found out that high-performing ANC facilities also tends to report high immunization outputs. For example, Muhoza (Ruhengeri) CS and Remera (Gasabo) CS shows consistently strong performance across both ANC and immunization indicators. Same case to Kagugu CS and Kinyinya CS reported high levels for all three outcomes.

However, some exceptions occurred and were noted. Whereas Hopital Croix du Sud reported a very high ANC volume (mean = 10,629) but it had a relatively modest immunization performance (mean DTP – 1,193;

MR2 = 1,139). Same case as well to Kacyiru CS that registered a large ANC volume (2,361) but having comparatively lower immunization counts. These disparities could be the result of inconsistent reporting, referral patterns or care delivery models unique to a certain facility.

Detailed facility-level results are provided in **Supplementary Table 1**.

Time-Series and Lagged Relationships

We analyzed the yearly facility averages of ANC new registrations with DTP3 and MR2 from 2017 to 2024 in order to evaluate the chronological alignment between ANC and immunization. In the trend analysis we did, from 2017 to 2022, there were very slight variations in the ANC and immunization indicators. The rapid increase of HMIS reporting coverage which brought in a large number of newly reporting, lower-volume facilities, was the reason for the apparent dramatic decreases in 2023-2024. Per-facility averages were decreased by this expansion, which may not have accurately reflected actual service decreases.

Pearson correlations were then computed between ANC new registrations and immunization outcomes under same-year and lagged assumptions.

For DTP3, the correlation with ANC new registrations was almost perfect in the same reporting year ($r = 0.997$), showing the fact that this vaccine is administered within a few months after birth. At a one-year lag, the correlation dropped to ($r = 0.834$), which in the same case, it represents a strong relationship but confirms that DTP3 uptake is most closely aligned with ANC in the same year. For MR2, which is normally given at 15-18 months of age, we expected a stronger relationship with the previous year's ANC cohort. Instead, the same year correlation was higher with an ($r = 0.993$) than the lag-1 correlation ($r = 0.821$). This pattern likely shows two key factors; first, the use of annual HMIS data, that aggregates across multiple birth cohorts and compresses the true 15-month vaccination schedule into either the same or following year; and second, the fact that facilities with strong service delivery, it tends to perform consistently well across both the ANC and immunization indicators within the same reporting year.

Figure 2. Time series of ANC, DTP3, and MR2 per facility averages, Rwanda HMIS 2017-2024

DTP3 vs ANC same year: 0.9966534595839521
 DTP3 vs ANC lag-1: 0.8341303092208763
 MR2 vs ANC same year: 0.9926986554045709
 MR2 vs ANC lag-1: 0.8212687051306089

As MR2 is typically given or administered at 15-18 months after birth, we tested whether lagging new registrations by two years would reveal a stronger cohort-level relationship. Instead, at a lag of two years, the correlation dropped sharply ($r \approx 0.39$) compared to $r \approx 0.82$ at lag-1, showing that the direct cohort linkage is largely lost by this point.

Several reasons likely explain why it is lower on lag 2; we made 3 different assumptions;

First, is the **Timing of MR2**; Normally, MR2 is recommended at 15-18 months after birth. In most cases, that falls into the following calendar year after ANC (lag-1), not two year later. Here Lag-2 would only capture cases where; a child's birth was late in year X, MR2 was delayed beyond the recommended schedule or even when the data system is reported late. These situations are far less common so the relationship is weaker.

Second assumption is the aggregation effect; my data is annual not monthly which means children born in the second half of the year might have MR2 in the same year as those born in the first half of the next year, blurring the real flag. Moreover, because of this annual grouping, the true ~15 month lag tends to look more like **Lag-1** in year-based data.

Finally, the last assumption we made is the effect of service linkage and cohort dilution; meaning here if a facility has generally strong ANC and immunization services, both MR2 and ANC will be high in the same year (and to some extent in the following year). Another point is that, by year 2 the direct connection between a specific ANC cohort and MR2 coverage is diluted by different things; one is different birth cohorts,

the other one is migration between service areas and the last one we thought about is the data inconsistencies.

The lag-2 analysis of ANC new registrations and MR2 coverage is provided in **Supplementary Figure 2**.

Discussion

This study examined the relationship between two things; antenatal care (ANC) service uptake and childhood immunization outcomes (DTP3 and MR2) using facility-level data from Rwanda's HMIS between 2017 and 2024. Several key findings found in our study: (i) ANC and immunization indicators are strongly and positively correlated at facility level, (ii) facilities with high ANC volumes generally also report strong immunization performance, with some exceptions, (iii) time-series analysis confirmed close alignment of ANC with immunization outcomes in the same year, while lagged associations decrease over time, and (iv) recent expansion in HMIS reporting coverage has altered per-facility averages, underscoring the need to interpret longitudinal trends with caution.

Interpretation of Correlation Patterns

The well-established continuum of mother and child health services is supported by the strong positive correlations shown between ANC indicators and immunization outcomes. Facilities that successfully register and monitor pregnant women also typically have higher immunization outputs for infants. The highest correlations with DTP3 and MR2 were found for ANC new registrations and early ANC contact (first trimester), suggesting how important of early maternal care involvement in providing continuity into infant immunization. This finding aligns with global evidence that early and repeated ANC visits not only improve maternal outcomes but also reinforce subsequent service utilization for children. In a study from Gebrehiwot et al. (2025) analyzed the 2019 mini-EDHS in Ethiopia and found that only 40% of children received full vaccinations, showing it to be lower than the 53% DTP3 coverage reported in the 2016 EDHS and far below the WHO/UNICEF estimates of 63% in 2020. Ethiopia's coverage rates also lagged behind the African regional average (DTP3 ~ 76%, measles ~70%) and neighboring countries such as Kenya (86% DTP3, 83% measles) and Uganda (89% DTP3, 95% measles) [23]. Importantly, in the study ANC visits were found as a significant predictor of child immunization uptake, with five or more visits substantially improving coverage; mirroring our findings that ANC service use is closely tied to immunization outcomes

However, the observed link indicates the overall quality and integration of service delivery within institutions rather than suggesting a direct causative pathway. Strong facilities probably have better record-keeping, outreach, staffing, and systems, all of which work together to increase ANC and vaccination uptake. On the other hand, establishments with operational or structural flaws might not function well in both areas.

Facility-Level Variability

This trend is backed up by the examination of the top 10 facilities by ANC registrations, which also shows certain exceptions. Strong performance in both ANC and immunization was shown by facilities including Remera (Gasabo) CS, Kagugu CS, and Muhoza (Ruhengeri) CS, showing integrated, high-capacity service delivery. Conversely, Kacyiru CS displayed comparable disparities to Hopital Croix du Sud, which reported disproportionately lower immunization volumes despite highly high ANC registrations. These occurrences could be the result of inconsistent reporting, referral patterns, or variations in service paradigms (ANC services drawing a lot of clients but vaccinations being given elsewhere, for example). Finding these

differences is crucial because they could be a sign of data quality issues, service fragmentation, or gaps in the connection between child and maternal health services.

Temporal Dynamics and Lag Analysis

A Time-series analysis from 2017 to 2022 showed that ANC and immunization trajectories were closely matched, confirming the close integration of maternal and child health services at facility level. The major decrease in per-facility averages starting in 2023 was caused by the expansion of HMIS reporting coverage, which included many new, smaller facilities, rather by actual service delivery decreases. This finding shows the importance of applying contextual awareness when analyzing and interpreting routine health data, especially when data systems are undergoing major modifications or reforms.

Lag analysis added further nuance. As expected, DTP3 showed an almost perfect correlation with ANC in the same year ($r = 0.997$), showing the short interval between birth and vaccine administration. MR2, typically delivered at 15–18 months, showed a strong lag-1 correlation ($r = 0.821$), but the highest correlation was still same-year ($r = 0.993$). The facility effect—facilities with strong service performance tend to excel simultaneously in ANC and immunization and annual data aggregation, which compresses the 15-month vaccination interval into either the same-year or the following year, can both explain this somewhat counterintuitive finding. At lag-2, the correlation dropped sharply ($r \approx 0.39$), consistent with the loss of direct cohort linkage beyond the expected immunization window. This pattern reinforces the importance of focusing on same-year and lag-1 analyses for monitoring ANC–immunization linkages, while recognizing that lag-2 associations are diluted by overlapping cohorts, migration, and data inconsistencies.

Implications for Policy and Practice

The results point to a number of useful applications. First, there seems to be a positive knock-on effect on vaccine coverage from strengthening ANC, especially early registration. Therefore, programs should provide special attention to outreach that motivates women to regularly and early get ANC. Second, identifying facilities with mismatched immunization and ANC performance can assist guide data quality reviews, integration projects, or focused supervision. Third, the 2023–2024 expansion of HMIS reporting coverage complicates longitudinal interpretation while offering richer national visibility; future monitoring frameworks should modify per-facility averages for reporting coverage.

Conclusion

This study provides robust evidence on how ANC performance is strongly associated with childhood immunization outcomes at the facility level in Rwanda. Which informs us that strengthening ANC particularly early and repeated visits not only improves maternal outcomes but also it appears to enhance the child immunization coverage. Facilities with mismatched performance shows areas to further investigation into service integration and the quality in how they report. Future analysis should leverage more granular HMIS data to refine lag assessments and explore causal pathways, but the findings already shows the critical role of strengthening and integrating maternal and child health services in achieving sustained coverage gains.

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